

Thermal Characterization of Phenylethynyl-Terminated Polyimide Nanocomposites Reinforced with Expanded Graphite

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SUMMARY: The thermal expansion behavior of intercalated graphite flake to the exfoliated graphite flake has been microscopically and thermomechanically demonstrated in real-time, showing dramatic linear expansion with the formation of nanoplatelets below 300°C. The dynamic mechanical properties, thermal expansion, glass transition behavior and thermal stability of the PETI-5 composites nanoreinforced with expanded graphite (EG) having different average particle sizes (1~19 μm size) and nanoparticle content (1~20 wt%) have been studied. The result indicates that PETI-5/EGV composites have greater storage modulus, lower CTE and higher thermal stability, especially at high concentration of EGV (~1 μm), than PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites with a relatively larger size of EG (~19 μm and ~7 μm). The thermal properties significantly depend on the concentration and size of the EG nanoplatelets.

KEYWORDS: Expanded graphite flakes, phenylethynyl-terminated polyimide, nanoplatelets, dynamic mechanical properties, thermal expansion behavior, glass transition temperature

INTRODUCTION

Much attention has been paid to new polymer materials with high performance and/or functionality for the purpose of improving the polymer properties and extending their applications as well, especially during the last decade. Nanocomposites are one of the most promising materials. Nanocomposites, in which the polymer matrix is filled with nanoreinforcing phases having dimensions typically in the range of 1~100 nm exhibit considerably higher mechanical properties with far lower concentration of reinforcements than the conventional counterparts [1,2]. After layered reinforcements with large aspect ratio are exfoliated and dispersed in a polymer matrix as nanoplatelets, the polymer composite materials have improved mechanical, thermal and barrier properties depending upon the type of nanoplatelets [3].

Like clay, graphite is layered mineral having a large aspect ratio. Graphite is a platelet carbon consisting of graphene sheets held together by weak van der Waals forces. Single crystal graphite has an elastic modulus of over 1 TPa, which is many times greater than nanoclay. Unlike clay, graphite is thermally and electrically conductive. Expandable graphite, which is composed of natural graphite flake intercalated with acid, can be expanded up to hundreds of times over its initial volume at high temperature, resulting in separation of the graphene sheets at the nanoscopic level along the *c* axis of graphene layers [4-5]. The intercalated graphite flake material is often called a graphite intercalation compound (GIC).

Phenylethynyl-terminated polyimide (PETI-5), which has been developed by the NASA Langley Research Center since 1994, has had considerable attention in aircraft for structural and electrical applications as a potential material for coating, adhesives, films, and composite matrix resins [6,7]. Among a series of PETI-5 polymers, it has been known that one with the molecular weight of 2500 g/mol has an excellent combination of processibility, high glass transition temperature, high toughness and mechanical, physical, chemical and thermal properties and adhesion at elevated temperature [8]. Several fundamental studies with this material have been reported by our research team [7,9-11] and others [12,13].

The objective of this study is to explore the real-time thermal expansion behavior of expandable graphite flake, to prepare nanocomposites consisting of expanded (or exfoliated) graphite nanoplatelets and a phenylethynyl-terminated polyimide, and also to extensively characterize them using various thermal analysis methods such as dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), thermomechanical analysis (TMA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The results of the thermal property investigation of the polyimide composites reinforced with expanded graphite nanoplatelets such as dynamic mechanical properties, thermal expansion behavior, glass transition temperature, and thermal stability will be presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials. Expandable graphite flakes (GrafGuard™ 160-50A) are supplied from UCAR Carbon Company (USA) after intercalated by a mixture of sulfuric acid and nitric acid. It is released from the supplier that the content of intercalant is about 22% by weight. The expansion volume per gram at 600°C is about 250 mm³ and the expanded graphite flakes contain the carbon content about 97%. Expanded graphite flakes (EG) were thermally prepared at 900°C in air and then finely pulverized using ultrasonication, ball-milling (alumina balls as grinding media), and vibratory-milling (zirconia balls as grinding media) techniques, respectively. It was found using a particle size analyzer (Masterizer 2000, Malvern Instrument, Ltd.) that the average particle sizes of the EG pulverized by means of each technique are approximately 19 μm, 7 μm and 1 μm, respectively. It has been found that the thickness of an EG nanoplatelet with a 1 μm particle size is about 5.4 nm and the aspect ratio is about 185.

The thermosetting PETI-5 oligomer used here was synthesized and supplied in the liquid form of an amic acid from Imitec, Inc. (Schenectady, NY). The ‘as-received’ PETI-5 is a random copolymer with a number-average molecular weight of 2500 g/mol, which is prepared from 3,4'-oxydianiline (ODA), 1,3-bis(3-aminophenoxy)benzene (APB), and 3,3', 4,4'-biphenyltetracarboxylic dianhydride (BPDA), endcapped with 4-phenylethynylphthalic anhydride (PEPA). The synthesis and chemistry of PETI-5 have been described in detail elsewhere [12]. The solids content in *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP) as solvent is about 35% by weight. Fig. 1 represents the chemical structures of the amic acid and polyimide of PETI-5.

Observations of the Expansion Behavior of Expandable Graphite Flakes. The real-time thermal behavior was observed on a hot-plate at 300°C using a high-speed digital camera (Coolpix 990, Nikon). A series of photos was obtained in a sub-second time scale for a single expandable graphite flake. A Thermomechanical Analyzer (TMA 2940, TA Instrument) was

also

PETI-5 Oligomer

and

PETI-5 Polyimide

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of phenylethynyl-terminated imide (PETI-5) oligomer and polymer.

utilized to investigate the onset temperature, rate and ratio of thermal expansion. The measurements were performed on a quartz stage from ambient temperature to 500°C at a heating rate of 2°C/min purging a N₂ gas of 50 cc/min. A standard expansion mode was used. The microstructure of the graphite flakes before and after the expansion was observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-5900, JEOL).

Preparation of PETI-5 Polyimide Composites Reinforced with EG Nanoplatelets. It is not easy to obtain a uniformly dispersed mixture of the EG with the PETI-5 oligomer by directly mixing the two components due to relatively high viscosity of the PETI-5 oligomer. Also, the EG particles can gradually segregate to the bottom layer during a long period of curing time during the fabrication in a mold. To solve such the problem, the EG was first uniformly dispersed in NMP using an ultrasonic bath. The mixture of EG/NMP was mixed well with the PETI-5 oligomer and then the NMP was completely removed at 202°C. The brittle yellowish solids of PETI-5 obtained were ground in a mortar.

The ground PETI-5/EG powder was placed in a steel mold. The PETI-5/EG composites were fabricated by a compression molding method using a hot-press (Carver 2518). The multi-step cure profile is shown in Fig. 2. The dimensions of each specimen are 77 mm in length, 13 mm in width, and 3.5 mm in thickness. The EG concentration in the composite was varied from 1 to 20 wt% depending on the pulverizing method. Each specimen was cut to the proper size for each analytical requirement using a low-speed diamond saw (Isomet™ Buehler Co.). Cured PETI-5 specimens without the EG were also prepared for comparison.

Thermal Analyses. The storage modulus, loss modulus and tan δ of cured PETI-5 control and PETI-5/EG composites were measured at temperatures up to 450°C in the vertical mode using a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA 893, TA Instrument). A heating rate of 2°C/min was used purging a N₂ gas of 50 cc/min. A fixed freq-

Fig. 2. Cure profile of PETI-5/EG

uency of 1 Hz was used. The oscillation amplitude composites in a compression mold. used was 0.2 mm.

A differential scanning calorimeter (DSC 910, TA Instrument) was used to examine the glass transition behavior of cured PETI-5 resin and PETI-5/EG composites. The measurements were done up to 400°C~450°C with a heating rate of 10°C/min purging a N₂ gas of 50 cc/min.

The thermal expansion behavior of cured PETI-5 control and the composites was observed up to 450°C by using a thermomechanical analyzer (TMA 2940, TA Instrument). The dimensions of each specimen are 3mm × 3mm × 3mm with a regular hexahedron form. A standard expansion probe was used under the normal force of 0.005 N loaded by itself. A heating rate of 2°C/min was used purging a N₂ gas of 50 cc/min throughout the work.

A thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA 951, TA Instrument) was also used to examine the thermal stability of each specimen. The measurements were done up to 900°C with a heating rate of 10°C/min purging a N₂ gas of 80 cc/min. An Energy-Filtering-Transmission Electron Microscopy (Carl Zeiss, EM912 Omega) was used to observe the EG nanoplatelets in the PETI-5 polyimide matrix. The magnification was 100000×.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Real-Time Observations of the Expansion Behavior. Fig. 3 represents scanning electron microphotographs showing the thermal expansion behavior of intercalated (expandable) graphite flakes (IG) and the expanded graphite flakes (EG) pulverized with different particle sizes by ultrasonication, ball-milling and vibratory-ball milling techniques, respectively. The inserted photos, which are taken with a high-speed digital camera, show the real-time expansion behavior of a single expandable graphite flake occurring on a hot-plate set to be 300°C.

Fig. 3. SEM observations of natural graphite flake (A), intercalated graphite flake (B) and expanded graphite flake (C) with different particles sizes pulverized using ultrasonication (D), ball-milling (E) and vibratory-milling (F) techniques. Real-time expansion is shown by

insertion.

The scale bar shows 5 μm in F and 10 μm (top) and 100 μm (bottom) in D and E, respectively.

Figs. 3(A), (B) and (C) represent the SEM results observed for natural graphite flakes (NG), IG and EG, respectively. The average flake size of the IG (B) is approximately 800~900 μm with a thickness of 80~120 μm . The aspect ratio is about 10. Each flake is built up with multi-platelets consisting of a number of very thin layers of submicrometer thick. It is likely that the aspect ratio of single crystal graphite is in the range of 100~1000. The multi-layers in the IG can be very rapidly expanded and exfoliated up to a few hundreds times their initial volume as a result of the vaporization of the intercalant in between the graphene sheets during the heat-treatment below 300°C and also of the thermal shock causing a puff-off of the lamellar structure in the crystalline graphene sheets. Fig. 3(C) shows the microstructure at the magnifications of 30 \times (top) and 1000 \times (bottom) for the EG after the heat-treatment of a single IG at 600°C. The EG is expanded along with the *c* axis of the graphene sheets and exhibits a worm-like or an accordion-like shape composed of multiple nano-scaled platelet layers held together at their edges. It is also observed that there are a large number of pores between the thin nanoplatelets.

As seen in the inserted photos, the thickness of a single IG is less than 0.1 mm before expanded (0 sec). It was found that the expansion proceeds along with the *c* axis and it is completed within 0.3 sec. The thickness of a single IG with multiple graphene sheets is dramatically increased up to 10 mm or longer after the expansion. As a result, it is expected that the expansion ratio is approximately 100 or greater.

Fig. 4 shows the thermal expansion behavior of a single IG studied by TMA. A single IG particle was used for each measurement. Each curve indicates the comparable expansion pattern of individual particles. The result informs on the onset temperature, rate and ratio of thermal expansion for the IG used in this work. The onset temperature of expansion is about 160°C~170°C. The expansion takes place in the range of 220°C~240°C most rapidly. The expansion ratio from the TMA measurement is observed to be 30~40, which is much less than expected. The following three reasons explain the fact. First, the flake is loaded by a minimum normal force of 0.005 N due to the TMA probe itself to the opposite direction of the expansion during the measurement. Second, the expansion proceeds in the twisting and bending form, not to the straightforward direction. Therefore the expansion is significantly suppressed under the probe during the measurement. Third, generally the TMA instrument is not sensitive enough as

Fig. 4. TMA results showing the expansion behavior of a single IG particle.

Fig. 5. TEM microphotograph of PETI-5/EG1B nanocomposite (100000 \times).

Fig. 5 shows the transmission electron microphotograph observed for a PETI-5/EG composite filled with the EG of 1 wt% pulverized using a ball-milling technique. The scale bar indicates 100 nm. As can be seen, the EG nanoplatelets of 20~50 nm in thickness are exfoliated and dispersed in the PETI-5 polyimide matrix. In a polymer/EG system, it is difficult to completely disperse the polymer molecules into the exfoliated galleries between the individual graphene layers, unlike in a polymer/clay nanocomposite system. The graphene layers theoretically separate by 3.354 Å. The distance does not change significantly unless ideally every single graphene layer is intercalated and exfoliated during processing. Even after the completion of the expansion or exfoliation process, completely exfoliated EG layers are hard to obtain. The inner layers of the flake may have a graphene structure consisting of multiple graphene sheets [14]. Consequently, the PETI-5/EG nanocomposites in the present study consist of multi-layered exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets uniformly dispersed in the PETI-5 polyimide matrix on the nano-scale.

Dynamic Mechanical Behavior. Fig. 6 shows the variation of the storage modulus as a function of temperature for the cured PETI-5, PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites. In the legend, the numbers (1, 3, 5 and 10) indicate the weight percent of the EG concentration in the composite. The suffixes, U and B, designate the ultrasonication and the ball-milling techniques used to prepare the EG particles, respectively.

Below the glass transition, the storage modulus of PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites is greater than that of PETI-5 control. The modulus shows the trend of an increase with increasing the EG concentration, as also informed from Table 1. The storage modulus of PETI-5/EG1U composite is slightly greater than that of PETI-5/EG1B counterpart below the glass transition. Above the glass transition, the storage modulus of the PETI-5/EG composites increases with increasing the EG concentration. The PETI-5/EG5U composite exhibits the greatest. The modulus of PETI-5/EG10 one is lower than that of PETI-5/EG5U above 250°C. Above the transition, the modulus of PETI-5/EG1U composite is greater than that of PETI-5/EG1B one. It is noted that the PETI-5 composites filled with the EG have the greater storage modulus than the unfilled counterpart over the temperature range measured.

Fig. 6. Plots of the storage modulus vs.

Fig. 7. Plots of the tan δ vs. temperature for

temperature for the cured PETI-5, PETI-5 the cured PETI-5, PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5 /EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites. /EGB composites.

The glass transition temperature (T_g) of a polymer matrix in a composite can be often determined from the peak maximum of a $\tan \delta$ curve. Fig. 7 shows the variation of the $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature. The T_g of PETI-5/EGU composites increases with increasing the EG concentration, showing the greatest at 5 wt%. In the range of 3~5 wt%, the uncured PETI-5 resin may be effectively incorporated in the galleries between the exfoliated graphene layers. Such the good dispersion of the EG nanoplatelets into the PETI-5 matrix may contribute to enhancing the storage modulus and the T_g of PETI-5/EGU composite. However, the T_g is decreased upon addition of 10 wt% EG due to poor dispersion at high concentration of relatively large-sized EG particles. The broad $\tan \delta$ peaks observed below 200°C are related with the β transition of PETI-5, as found earlier [15].

Fig. 8. Plots of the storage modulus vs. temperature for PETI-5/EGV composites. Fig. 9. Plots of the $\tan \delta$ vs. temperature for PETI-5/EGV composites.

Fig. 8 represents the variation of the storage modulus as a function of temperature for PETI-5 control and PETI-5/EGV composites. The suffix V designates the vibratory-milling technique used to prepare the EG particles, which has the smallest particle size of about 1 μm . Below 250°C, the storage modulus increases with increasing the EGV content, as found in a series of PETI-5/EGU specimens. It has also been found that the $\log E'$ values of the PETI-5/EGV composites are relatively greater than those of the PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB counterparts. This may be due to the smaller size effect of EG particles finely dispersed without segregation into a PETI-5 matrix even at higher loading. Above the glass transition, the modulus also increases with the EG concentration. Fig. 9 shows the variation of the $\tan \delta$ against temperature. The T_g values of PETI-5/EGV composites are greater than that of PETI-5 control, showing the greatest at 20 wt%. The dynamic mechanical results suggest that the nanoplatelets surrounding the PETI-5 resin in the exfoliated layers may contribute to decreasing the flexibility of the PETI-5 molecular chains and to increasing the stiffness of the composite, resulting in the enhancement of the storage modulus and the T_g .

Table 1 summarizes the values of the storage modulus measured for the PETI-5/EG composites. The values of $\log E'$ (GPa) seen in Figs. 6 and 8 were converted into E' (GPa) in tubular data for inspecting the quantitative variation of the storage modulus. Below the T_g , the

storage modulus is improved by 0.707 GPa at 100°C and by 0.659 GPa at 200°C from PETI-5 control to PETI-5/EG20V composite, respectively. The % improvements of the storage modulus from the PETI-5 control are about 79% at 100°C and 92% at 200°C for the PETI-5/EG20V composites, respectively, showing the most prominent improvement among the specimens used. Also, the storage modulus depends on the size of EG nanoparticles reinforced in the PETI-5 composites.

Table 1. Results of the storage modulus for the PETI-5/EG composites at 100°C and 200°C.

Composite Specimen	Storage Modulus (GPa) at 100°C	% Improvement from control	Storage Modulus (GPa) at 200°C	% Improvement from control
PETI-5 Control	0.897	0	0.716	0
PETI-5/EG1U	1.133	26.3	0.944	31.8
PETI-5/EG3U	1.193	33.0	0.981	37.0
PETI-5/EG5U	1.255	39.9	1.070	49.4
PETI-5/EG10U	1.276	42.3	1.116	55.9
PETI-5/EG1V	0.939	4.7	0.768	7.3
PETI-5/EG3V	0.902	0.6	0.746	4.2
PETI-5/EG5V	1.295	44.4	1.095	52.9
PETI-5/EG20V	1.604	78.8	1.375	92.0

Thermal Expansion Behavior. Fig. 10 shows the dimensional change as a function of temperature, indicating the thermal expansion behavior of the cured PETI-5 resin, PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites. It is observed that there is an obvious break in the range of 250°C~280°C depending on the glass transition behavior of each specimen. The change of the T_g studied by TMA and other thermal analyses is discussed in more detail in the later part of this paper. All the specimens exhibit a linear increase of the dimensional change as a function of temperature below the glass transition region. The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) obtained for PETI-5/EG composites below T_g is slightly lower than that for PETI-5 control, with the exception of PETI-5/EG10U specimen, as shown in Table 2. The CTE has been determined from the linear portion of each TMA thermogram below T_g , in the glass transition region of the 10°C range, and above T_g . The temperature range at each region for determining the CTE is indicated in the table. The expansion in this temperature range is mainly attributed to the cured PETI-5 resin. The CTE change is clearly distinguishable at the transition, which is most sensitive to thermally activated molecular motion.

In the transition region, each specimen exhibits different behavior of the thermal expansion. In the PETI-5/EGU composites, the CTE decreases with increasing the EG concentration. At 10 wt%, the CTE remarkably increases showing the greatest among a series of EGU specimens, as seen in the PETI-5/EG10U specimen. It is noticeable that such the thermal expansion is mainly governed by the EG distributed in the PETI-5 resin. At high concentration of the large-sized EG particles, the EG nanoplatelets may more or less exist without successfully uniform dispersion due to possible segregation in the polymer resin. Also, it may be expected that there are a large number of pores with sufficient free-volume between the platelets. Such the EG platelets may be further expandable with assistance of the neighboring PETI-5. In other words, the thermal expansion of PETI-5 may, to some extent, accelerate the

thermal expansion of the EG platelets by shoving out the graphene sheets incompletely filled

with the resin but filled with pores to be

Fig. 10. TMA results for cured PETI-5, PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites. Fig. 11. TMA results showing the thermal expansion for PETI-5/EGV composites.

Table 2. Values of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) for the PETI-5/EG composites.

Composite Specimen	CTE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{m}/\text{°C}$)		
	Below T_g (50~200 °C)	From the transition region	Above T_g (300~350 °C)
PETI-5 Control	51.6	1249 (261 \square ~271 \square)	152
PETI-5/EG1U	47.7	1109 (270 \square ~280 \square)	201
PETI-5/EG3U	49.4	985 (272 \square ~282 \square)	215
PETI-5/EG5U	48.7	896 (275 \square ~285 \square)	205
PETI-5/EG10U	53.1	2185 (262 \square ~272 \square)	-57
PETI-5/EG1V	51.7	1049 (265 \square ~275 \square)	197
PETI-5/EG3V	47.0	908 (268 \square ~278 \square)	202
PETI-5/EG5V	50.6	716 (270 \square ~280 \square)	225
PETI-5/EG20V	50.7	600 (277 \square ~287 \square)	214

further expanded. As a result, the expansion behavior of PETI-5/EG10U is similar with that of the expandable graphite flake (IG) in Fig. 4, with the exception of a shift of expanding temperature roughly from 220 °C to 250 °C due to the presence of the PETI-5. Therefore, it is reasonable that the segregation due to poor dispersion may take place in the EG10U specimen, which has not observed in the PETI-5/EGV specimen with a finer particle size of EG.

Fig. 11 represents the expansion behavior of PETI-5/EGV composites with various EG contents. As seen from the result with less than 5 wt% EG concentration in Fig. 10, the thermal expansion decreases with increasing the EG concentration. As listed in Table 2, the change of the CTE below T_g is slight. However, the more distinguishable thermal expansion takes place in the glass transition region. The CTE values are significantly reduced by increasingly incorporating the EG particles of about 1 μm . This may be explained by that the small-sized EG nanoplatelets are uniformly dispersed in the PETI-5 matrix on the nano-scale without significant segregation or pores occupied by free-volume. It is found that the CTE values of the EGV series in the transition region are lower than those of the EGU series at corresponding concentrations. The thermal expansion of the PETI-5 may be somewhat retarded by the thermally stable EG

nanoreinforcement surrounding the resin, resulting in a shift of the transition break to a higher temperature. In the transition region, the CTE does not increase dramatically but decreases, unlike the behavior shown for the PETI-5/EG10U specimen in Fig. 10. The result also suggests that at high concentration of EG particles the PETI-5/EGV composites are thermomechanically more stable than the PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites having a large particle size. Beyond the transition region, the thermal expansion becomes much smaller than that in the transition region but greater than that below T_g due to high temperature effect.

Glass Transition Behavior. Fig. 12 shows the DSC thermograms measured for the cured PETI-5, PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites. The T_g was determined from the inflection point of the endothermic change occurring in the temperature range of 265°C~280°C. The T_g of the PETI-5/EGU composites is greater than that of the cured PETI-5 up to 5 wt% and then decreases at 10 wt%. It is likely that a similar trend of an increase with the EG concentration is seen in the PETI-5/EGV composites, as shown in Fig. 13. Such the glass transition behavior studied by DSC is also supported by DMA and TMA results described earlier.

Fig. 12. DSC thermograms for PETI-5, PETI-5/EGU and PETI-5/EGB composites.

Fig. 13. DSC thermograms for various EGU and PETI-5/EGV composites.

Table 3 summarizes the T_g values measured using DSC, TMA and DMA, respectively. In the TMA thermograms (Figs. 10 and 11), the T_g was determined from the inflection point of the dimensional change in the transition region. In the DMA thermograms (Figs. 7 and 9), the T_g was determined from the maximum of $\tan \delta$ peak.

Table 3. A comparison of the T_g values (°C) determined by DSC, TMA and DMA methods.

Specimen	DSC	TMA	DMA	Specimen	DSC	TMA	DMA
Cured PETI-5	268	267	276	PETI-5/EG1B	273	268	284
PETI-5/EG1U	279	275	289	PETI-5/EG1V	261	267	289
PETI-5/EG3U	279	277	290	PETI-5/EG3V	267	272	287
PETI-5/EG5U	277	279	295	PETI-5/EG5V	268	273	286
PETI-5/EG10U	265	264	289	PETI-5/EG20V	281	283	297

Comparing the T_g values, the T_g obtained with the dynamic DMA method appears at higher temperature than that with the DSC or TMA method, which is relatively static. The T_g difference may be in the range of 8°C~28°C depending on the specimen and the methodology.

The DMA method is, in general, more sensitive to large-scale molecular motions, even though the three methods are all based upon the thermal motions of polymer chains [11]. The frequency applied in the DMA is normally much greater than that in the DSC, resulting in a shift of the $\tan \delta$ maximum to a higher temperature.

Thermal Stability. It has been observed that up to 700°C the thermal stability of PETI-5/EGU composites with the EG content less than 3 wt% is slightly higher than that of the cured PETI-5 control. However, the PETI-5/EGU composites with the EG contents of 5 wt% and 10 wt% have the lower thermal stability than the PETI-5 control. In the PETI-5/EGV composites, the thermal stability slightly increases with increasing the EG concentration up to 700°C. The result indicates that the initial decomposition temperature of the PETI-5 control and less concentrated EGV composites, which is mostly attributed to the PETI-5, is increased about 50°C~100°C in the PETI-5/EG20V composite.

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